

Post-Test Tasks and Grading Rubrics

This document contains selected post-test tasks alongside their corresponding grading rubrics. The programming tasks are presented in both Java and Kotlin. All materials have been translated into English from the original German instrument. Minor syntax errors, such as missing semicolons or omitted closing curly braces, are not penalized. Grading rubrics apply equally to both the Java and Kotlin groups unless explicitly stated otherwise.

Task 1: Classes and Objects

Consider the following code:

Java:

```
1 class Number {
2     int value;
3     String description;
4
5     Number(int value, String description) {
6         this.value = value;
7         this.description = description;
8     }
9 }
10
11 Number number1 = new Number(10, "Ten");
12 Number number2 = new Number(20, "Twenty");
13 number2 = number1;
14 number1.value = 15;
```

Kotlin:

```
1 class Number(var value: Int, val description: String)
2
3 var number1 = Number(10, "Ten")
4 var number2 = Number(20, "Twenty")
5 number2 = number1
6 number1.value = 15
```

Task Description: State the value of each of the following expressions after the above code has executed:

- number1.value:
- number2.value:
- number1.description:
- number2.description:

Grading Rubric: The total score for this task is 6.0 points. Each correct answer is awarded 1.5 points.

Task 2: Inheritance

A company represents its company vehicles using the following code:

Java:

```
1 class Car {
2     Manufacturer manu; // Manufacturer details
3     int seats; // Number of seats
4     double price; // Price in Euros
5
6     Car(Manufacturer manu, int seats) {
7         this.manu = manu;
8         this.seats = seats;
9         this.price = 5000.0;
10    }
11
12    void display() {
13        System.out.println("Manufacturer " + manu + " costs " + price);
14        System.out.println("Seats: " + seats);
15    }
16 }
17
18 class Transporter {
19     Manufacturer manu; // Manufacturer details
20     double payload; // Payload in tons
21     double price; // Price in Euros
22
23     Transporter(Manufacturer manu, double payload) {
24         this.manu = manu;
25         this.payload = payload;
26         this.price = 7000.0;
27     }
28
29     void display() {
30         System.out.println("Manufacturer " + manu + " costs " + price);
31         System.out.println("Payload: " + payload);
32     }
33 }
```

Kotlin:

```
1 class Car(
2     val manu: Manufacturer, // Manufacturer details
3     val seats: Int // Number of seats
4 ) {
5     var price: Double = 5000.0 // Price in Euros
6
7     fun display() {
8         println("Manufacturer $manu costs $price")
9         println("Seats: $seats")
10    }
11 }
12
13 class Transporter(
14     val manu: Manufacturer, // Manufacturer details
15     val payload: Double // Payload in tons
16 ) {
```

```

17     var price: Double = 7000.0 // Price in Euros
18
19     fun display() {
20         println("Manufacturer $manu costs $price")
21         println("Payload: $payload")
22     }
23 }

```

Note: You may abbreviate names as long as they are used consistently and their meaning remains clear. Java only: `System.out.println` can be abbreviated to `println`.

Task Description a): Identify the common properties and methods of the two classes and combine them into a shared superclass named `Vehicle`.

Grading Rubric: The total score for this task is 10.0 points. Because inheritance and initialization syntax differ between the two languages, separate rubrics are provided:

Java:

Category	Assessment Criteria	Points
Class Declaration	Correctly declares an inheritable class named <code>Vehicle</code> .	2.0
Fields	Correctly declares the shared fields and ensures they are accessible to subclasses.	2.0
Constructor	Correctly enables object instantiation by defining a constructor that initializes the shared fields.	2.0
Method Signature	Correctly declares the shared method (appropriate return type, name, and empty parameter list).	2.0
Method Implementation	Correctly implements the shared behavior within the method body.	2.0

Kotlin:

Category	Assessment Criteria	Points
Class Declaration	Correctly declares a class named <code>Vehicle</code> (2.0 pts) and ensures it is inheritable using <code>open</code> or <code>abstract</code> (1.0 pt).	3.0
Properties	Correctly declares the shared properties (2.0 pts) and ensures they are initializable via the primary constructor and accessible (1.0 pt).	3.0
Method Signature	Correctly declares the shared method (appropriate return type, name, empty parameter list) and ensures it is overridable.	2.0
Method Implementation	Correctly implements the shared behavior within the method body.	2.0

Task Description b): Modify the `Car` and `Transporter` classes so that they inherit from `Vehicle` and maintain the same behavior. Use the `super` keyword to avoid code duplication where appropriate.

Grading Rubric: The maximum score for this task is 10.0 points. Each of the two subclasses is evaluated out of 6.0 points (allowing a total raw score of up to 12.0), providing a buffer to

accommodate minor student mistakes:

Category	Assessment Criteria	Points
Class Declaration & Inheritance	Correctly declares the subclass and establishes inheritance from the superclass.	2.0
Shared Fields / Properties	Correctly initializes shared fields/properties by passing them to the superclass constructor.	1.0
Specific Field / Property	Correctly declares the field/property specific to the subclass.	1.0
Method Extension	Correctly overrides the method by invoking the superclass's implementation first, followed by the subclass-specific extension.	2.0

Task Description c): Define a `ParkingLot` class. It should be able to store an arbitrary number of cars and transporters. Write a method that returns the most expensive vehicle. A `NoSuchElementException` should be thrown if there are no vehicles in the parking lot.

Grading Rubric: The maximum score for this task is 10.0 points. The rubric provides up to 11.0 raw points, providing a buffer to accommodate minor student mistakes:

Category	Assessment Criteria	Points
Class Declaration	Correctly declares the class.	1.0
Collection Declaration	Correctly declares and initializes a mutable <code>List</code> or <code>ArrayList</code> that stores <code>Vehicle</code> objects.	2.0
Method Signature	Correctly declares the method with an appropriate name, an empty parameter list, and <code>Vehicle</code> as a return type.	1.0
Precondition	Correctly checks the collection state and throws a <code>NoSuchElementException</code> if the list is empty.	1.0
Temporary Variable	Correctly declares and initializes a temporary variable to hold a reference to the currently most expensive vehicle.	1.0
Loop	Correctly iterates over the collection (binds the current object, progresses to the end, and respects collection bounds).	2.0
Maximum Logic	Correctly determines the most expensive vehicle by comparing the price field/property (1.0 pt) and updates the temporary reference accordingly (1.0 pt).	2.0
Return Statement	Correctly returns the reference to the most expensive vehicle after the iteration ends.	1.0